

PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY IS THE MAIN ISSUE IN THE AREA OF PEDAGOGY

Xidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17323833>

Annotatsiya

Hozirgi vaqtda ta'lim tizimi va elektron ma'lumotlar bazasi hamda keng ko'lamli ma'lumotlar asosida aholi ma'lum bir bilimga ega bo'lmoqda. Talaba-muhandislar nafaqat universitetda o'qishga, balki ish joylarida ham har qachongidan ham ko'proq amaliyot o'tashga intilyaptilar, chunki o'qishni kasbiy mobillik bilan integratsiya qilish talabalar bilimi va amaliyot tajribasini oshirishning asosiy mezonidir. Shu sababli, qishloq xo'jaligida talaba-muhandislarning kasbiy mobilligini oshirish uchun integratsiyalashgan ta'limning pedagogik metodologiyasi zarurdir. Bundan tashqari, kelajakda kerakli mutaxassis bo'lish uchun kasbiy mobillik bilan universitetda tahsil olish zarurdir.

Kalit so'zlar: muhandislik talabalari, mutaxassislik, kasbiy harakatchanlik, ta'lim tizimi, o'qishning kasbiy mobillik bilan integratsiyasi.

Abstract

In present time the population are being more educated and modernized with updated education system and vast data through electronic data-basis. The engineering students are eager not only study at the university but also work at the workplaces to practice more than ever before because integration of study with professional mobility is the main issue to improve students' knowledge and practice experience. That's why, we need a pedagogical methodology for the integration education to improve professional mobility of the engineering students in the area of agriculture. Besides, professional mobility is in need for the time of studies in order to be needful specialist in the future.

Key words: the engineering students, specialty, professional mobility, education system, integration of study with professional mobility.

Аннотация

В настоящее время население становится всё более образованным и модернизированным благодаря обновленной системе образования и обширным данным, доступным через электронную базу данных. Студенты инженерных специальностей стремятся не только учиться в университете, но и работать на рабочих местах, поскольку интеграция обучения с профессиональной мобильностью является ключевым фактором для улучшения знаний и практического опыта студентов. Поэтому нам необходима педагогическая методика интеграционного образования, которая позволит повысить профессиональную мобильность студентов-инженеров в области сельского хозяйства. Кроме того, профессиональная мобильность необходима во время обучения, чтобы стать востребованными специалистами в будущем.

Ключевые слова: студенты инженерных специальностей, специальность, профессиональная мобильность, система образования, интеграция обучения с профессиональной мобильностью.

Introduction

Currently, phenomena characterizing the quality of a specialist's professional activity are of special importance in modern pedagogical science. This focuses on student-centered, inquire-based learning, critical thinking, personalized learning experience, utilizing technology, creativity, practical problem-solving at the workplaces. Furthermore, professional mobility is of particular interest, which is more often encountered in the context of pedagogical research. This is due to several factors: the specifics of social procurement, employer requirements oriented towards the dynamics of the modern labor market, the general situation with the types of professions that are

particularly in demand for the new conditions of global cataclysms and the adoption of strategic measures in professional spheres - the IT sphere, industrial areas of activity and others. What's more, the employer seeks to hire an employee not only as a good specialist in their field of expertise, but also as a person who can most effectively apply their existing competencies and acquire new ones, subject to continuous development and the emergence of new modifications. Moreover, new modifications of competencies must inevitably and quickly arise on the basis of social, psychological and economic aspirations for the dynamic development of outdated technologies in various areas of professional mobility.

Literature Review

The definition of professional mobility appears as a type of social mobility. Since the 1930s, professional mobility has been studied in the context of social mobility. The founder of mobility as a personal quality is P.A. Sorokin. The author himself defined social mobility as: "... any transition of an individual or social object (value), i.e., everything, what is created or modified by human activity, from one social position to another, issues of professional mobility were considered by such scientists as E. Durkheim, M. Weber, I. O. Martynyuk, V. N. Shubkina, V. A. Yadov. Researchers E. Durkheim and M. Weber claimed the main issues of the phenomenon in the context of the functional approach to the analysis of professional mobility as a social phenomenon. I.O. Martynyuk, V.N. Shubkina, and V.A. Yadov examine professional mobility through the problem of job search, student professional selection, adaptation, and improving the qualification level of specialists. Those scientists emphasize the importance of professional mobility as a necessary condition and quality at various stages of professional development and career building, in situations of professional self-determination of university graduates, job search, adaptation in the workplace, and professional development. Furthermore, in studies analyzing the areas of manifestation of mobility, it is possible to identify the types of mobility encountered by authors: social mobility – the movement of individuals, social groups; pedagogical mobility - presupposes the teacher's ability to organize communications with all subjects of the educational and upbringing process in an educational institution Professional mobility is the movement of an individual within the socio-professional structure of society. When examining professional mobility, authors distinguish between the following types: Horizontal and vertical mobility. Horizontal professional mobility refers to the transition of an individual from one professional group to another, located at the same level in terms of pay and professional prestige (I.V.Nikiforova.2023:261-262).

What's more, a characteristic feature of foreign studies of professional mobility is the use of similar terms related to the personal and professional characteristics of a specialist: flexibility, adaptability, variability, versatility, etc. Thus, the analysis of the research by the authors Savickas M.L. and Porfeli E.J. reveals mobility not as a personal characteristic, but as a result of professional actions and new conditions arising in professional mobility. In this regard, the dynamics of changes in professional personality traits related to adaptability and flexibility are examined. Among the foreign researchers, Savickas M.L. and Porfeli E.J. Experiments have shown that to successfully and effectively complete their tasks, a specialist must possess skills such as communication, the ability to make quick and clear decisions, and the ability to work in a team. Besides, one component of adaptability is commitment. It allows one to consider and evaluate the potential for future resource use and take action on situations that have not yet occurred, ensuring that opportunities are realized and risks are avoided. Interest gives you the opportunity to analyze your own capabilities, while control allows you to keep a close eye on the situation.

Competence of professional mobility

An analysis of studies on the components of professional mobility revealed that authors, when classifying them, rely on mental functions, or individual psychological qualities of the individual. Thus, L.A. Amirova identifies the following components of professional mobility: "1.

Cognitive component (professional and pedagogical knowledge underlying professional competence). 2. Operational and activity-based (mastery of teaching and educational technologies and methods necessary for a teacher to successfully adapt to various professional situations). 3. Regulatory (development of personality traits necessary for successful adaptation and self-realization in various professional situations).

K.I. Bezymenova identified several components based on personality traits and abilities:

"1. Activity – readiness for action, mastering new forms and types of activity, as the basis of professional and pedagogical efficiency. 2. Adaptability – the ability to adapt to changing conditions of activity.

3. Willingness to change one's life and activities. 4. Openness—an inclination toward the new and the unknown, a rejection of stereotypes. 5. Communication skills—the ability and willingness to establish new connections and contacts with educational stakeholders; 6. Creativity—a creative approach to the environment and one's own activities, a willingness to transform them."

Research methods

In the context of professional mobility, there are following ideas are revealed:

Conclusion

The work and study integration involves the young engineering students be optimistic for their future job accomplishments because professional mobility may be able to help the engineering students to discover innate talents in the field of agriculture for innovative cultivation in the salted fields to be given a life for plants to be planted and get a harvest. Besides, during the professional mobility the engineering students may invent how to get a great amount of fruits and vegetables from far reaching lands where there no water supply. Furthermore, creativity cannot

be done in time of acquisition of theoretical knowledge at the university, that's why, they need to do practice in the agricultural fields and industries to think creatively.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Амирова Л.А. Проблема профессиональной мобильности педагога и перспективные ориентиры ее развития // Образование и наука. 2009. № 8. С. 89.
2. Гофман А.Б. Социологическая энциклопедия. М., 2003. С. 38.
3. Зеер Э.Ф., Профессиональная мобильность как интегральное качество субъекта инновационной деятельности. М., 2015. № 5. С. 204.
4. Калиновский Ю.И. Праксиология исследовательской деятельности. Монография. Соликамск: изд-во СГПИ, 2008. С. 236.
5. Климов Е.А. «Потемки» и «светильники» в становлении профессионала. – Москва: Изд-во МПСИ, 2007. – 192 с.
6. Кормильцева М.В. Психологические детерминанты профессиональной мобильности личности. Образование и наука. Известия УРО РАО. – 2009. – № 4(61). – С. 72–77.
7. Родионова Е.А. Психологические факторы эффективности сотрудников современного предприятия // Terra Linguistica. 2011. №124.
8. Слепко Ю.Н. Содержание понятия «Эффективность профессиональной деятельности» // Ярославский педагогический вестник. – 2010. – Т. II, № 4. – С. 193–197.
9. Сорокин П.А. Социальная мобильность. – Москва: Academia, 2005. – 588 с.
10. Троицкая Ю.В. Профессиональная мобильность: российский и зарубежный опыт оперирования термином. – Педагогическое образование в России. – 2014. – № 9. – С. 122–126.
11. Savickas M.L. (1997). Career adaptability: An integrative construct for life-span, life-space theory. The Career Development Quarterly, 45, 247–259.